

DICTIONARIES OF PEDAGOGICAL TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK AND THEIR FUNCTIONS.

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Annotation: Dictionary - 1) a set of words, vocabulary, existing in a particular language, its regional or social dialect, found in the works of this or that writer; 2) a book in which words (or morphemes, phrases, phrases, etc.) are placed in a certain order (alphabetical, thematic), descriptive units, their origin, meanings, spelling, pronunciation, stylistic affiliation, translation into other languages. Dictionaries play an important role in the field of spiritual culture, reflecting the knowledge acquired by a society over a period of time. Pedagogical dictionaries - classify terms in the field of pedagogy.

New words: phrases, expressions, pedagogical terms, pedagogical lexicographic sources, international pedagogical terminology, education, monolingual pedagogical dictionary, multilingual / bilingual pedagogical dictionary, monolingual encyclopedic dictionary.

Problems in the field of pedagogical terminology can not be solved without understanding the essence of the categories "term", "concept", "system" terms or "terminology". it is defined by a word or phrase. A phrase is a term (Lat. terminus - "boundary", "boundary"). In fact, pedagogical terminology and concepts are crucial for the development of pedagogy. deals with the output.

Pedagogical lexicographic sources and consideration of the following issues:

- Types of pedagogical lexicographic sources; their elements and parameters;
- The basics of building pedagogical lexicographic sources and the possibility of using computer technology;
- Development and formation of algorithms for pedagogical creation of lexicographic sources; planning and organization of lexical and graphic activities;
- Selection of terms and formation of pedagogical lexicographic source;
- variants of interpretation of different terminological units, different types of dictionaries;
- Typology of pedagogical lexicographic sources;
- Consistency and consistency in international pedagogical terminology;

It should be noted that the function of pedagogical terms in dictionaries is as follows:

- Definition of pedagogical terms and connections between them;
- Analysis and modeling of the system of pedagogical terms based on the identified concepts and their relationship;
- Conditions for creating an image of the system of terms through diagrams
- definition of terms, definition of symbols (mainly terms) one or more languages for each pedagogical concept;
- Identification and presentation of terminological information in print and electronic forms (terminography) (M. Pottsi, 1999)

Use of new communication and computer technologies in the field of definition of developing pedagogical terminology in the process of professional pedagogical communication;

The transmission and exchange of knowledge between people of different cultures and speakers of different languages is aimed at studying the following aspects:

- knowledge of pedagogical terminology and pedagogical science (pedagogical concept) and "pedagogical term", conceptual analysis of pedagogical terminology, structural principles of pedagogical terminology, conceptual models of terminology, terminological approach to presentation, combination of scientific and pedagogical ontological and terminological approaches creation of information systems, etc.);

- Management of information resources of pedagogical knowledge (definition of contextual information, automatic procedures for obtaining pedagogical terminology). Pedagogical terminology, terminological bases, data, their use in conceptual indexing; relationship between text documents in the field of pedagogy and education and international pedagogical terminology, thesauruses for automatic indexing: structure, development and use, terminology logical means, creation of machine banks of pedagogical terminology, etc.);

- Pedagogical terminology in terms of the process of professional intercultural pedagogical communication and knowledge transfer;

- International pedagogical terminology: problems of localization and internationalization in contrast to global and regional;

- pedagogical terminology in terms of development global computer networks;

- Information society of pedagogical terminology in multimedia (multilingual terminological bases in the field of pedagogy and education, their creation and

activity; exchange of terminological data and the role of terminological infrastructure in multimedia age);

- Approaches to the presentation of scientific and pedagogical knowledge; problems of conceptual navigation in multimedia multicultural information research and educational spaces;

From the point of view of information, all information about the terms in the lexicographic pedagogical source is considered as follows:

- scientific-pedagogical (information concept about scientific pedagogy);

- Linguistic (characterized by features such as etymological information, semantically close terms, history of origin. Term, history of use of the term, usage of the term, foreign equivalents, grammatical features of the term, use of examples, etc.);

- cultural (reflected in features such as context). Use in a particular pedagogical culture, regional data, etc.)

According to the accepted parameters, pedagogical lexicographic sources are structured as follows:

1. **Monolingual pedagogical dictionary** (short general dictionary of pedagogical terms or terminology, created in the field of pedagogy).

For example: 1) Glossary of US Educational Terminology (Assefa) Glossary of United States Educational Terminology Mariam Assefa, PresidentWorld Education Services, New York; 2) Educational Terminology. zur learn: line Homepage, Educational Terminology. betreut durch John Eccleston .; 3) Educational Terminology Alphabetical index of educational terms.ADMISSION CRITERIA; 4) Educational terminology Eurydice; 5) Glossary of United States Educational Terminology.

2. **Multilingual / bilingual pedagogical dictionary** (a brief general translation dictionary of pedagogical terms or terminological expressions, collection. Examples: 1) Finnish-English Educational Terminology Glossary - Finnish-English education Glossary of Terminology: Finnish-English Educational Terminology Glossary FAST-US-5 US Education Survey FAST 177 Area Studies Program, Department of Translation Studies; 2) Educational terminology; Hungary OSEAS EUROPE EDUCATIONAL TERMINOLOGY. HUNGARY. Types of institutions, ovoda (kindergarten), iskola (school), altalanos iskola (primary school, general school);

3. **Monolingual encyclopedic dictionary, reference dictionary (a scientific-pedagogical lexicographic source** containing a systematized set of

knowledge on pedagogy, public education and related disciplines, arranged in alphabetical order; thematic (systematic) or alphabetical-thematic order;

briefly reveals the general theory of pedagogy, its history, specific disciplines, describes the system and state of education. For example: 1) V.V. 2-volume Russian pedagogical encyclopedia named after Davydov, M. : BRE, 1993. 2) DICTIONARY OF EDUCATION PLUS (Server) (includes a practical dictionary of terms in the field of pedagogical research, a bibliographic commentary for each defined term, as well as excerpts from articles describing the context in which the term is used) <http://macwe.umich.edu/plus/> (located at the University of Michigan).

4. Multilingual / bilingual encyclopedic dictionary, a dictionary (pedagogical lexicographic source, which includes a systematized set of knowledge on pedagogy, folklore and related disciplines, briefly discloses general information . Pedagogical theory, its history, individual disciplines, description of the education system and status in different countries). For example: 1. The Learner's English - Russian Dictionary of Education / English - 1998. 2. School English-Russian and Russian-English Dictionary, 2000

EDUCATION (as a pedagogical phenomenon) - the purposeful professional activity of the teacher, contributes to the maximum development of the child's personality, his entry into the context of modern culture, becoming a subject of his life, the formation of his motives and values. In dictionaries of comparable languages we can find as follows, we have interpreted it in connection with its types:

TARBIYA (pedagogik hodisa sifatida) - o'qituvchining maqsadli kasbiy faoliyati, bolaning shaxsiyatining maksimal rivojlanishiga, uning zamonaviy madaniyat kontekstiga kirishiga, o'z hayotining sub'ektiga aylanishiga, uning motivlari va qadriyatlarining shakllanishiga hissa qo'shadi. Pedagogika sohasidagi "Tarbiya" atamasi qiyoslanayotgan tillardagi lug'atlarda quyudagicha uchratishimiz mumkin, uning turlari bilan bog'lab talqin qildik:

<p>Ma'naviy tarbiya - insonning barqaror va barkamol rivojlanishini ta'minlaydigan hayotga bo'lgan qadriyatli munosabatni shakllantirish.</p>	<p>Spiritual upbringing is the formation of a valuable attitude to life that ensures the sustainable and harmonious development of a person</p>
<p>Axloqiy tarbiya - axloqiy munosabatlarning shakllanishi, ularni takomillashtirish qobiliyati va ijtimoiy talablar va me'yorlarga muvofiq harakat qilish qobiliyati, odatiy, kundalik axloqiy xulq-atvorning mustahkam tizimi.</p>	<p>Moral education is the formation of moral relations, the ability to improve them and the ability to act in accordance with social requirements and norms, a strong system of ordinary, everyday moral behavior</p>
<p>Siyosiy ta'lim - davlatlar, millatlar, partiyalar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni, ularni ma'naviy, axloqiy va axloqiy pozitsiyalardan anglash qobiliyatini aks ettiruvchi o'quvchilarning siyosiy ongini shakllantirish.</p>	<p>Political education is the formation of students' political consciousness, which reflects the relationship between states, nations, parties, their ability to understand them from a spiritual, moral and ethical standpoint.</p>
<p>Huquqiy ta'lim - huquqiy madaniyat va huquqiy xulq-atvorni shakllantirish jarayoni, bu yuridik umuminsoniy ta'limni amalga oshirish, huquqiy nihilizmni yengish, qonunga bo'ysunuvchi xulq-atvorni shakllantirishdan iborat.</p>	<p>Legal education is a process of formation of legal culture and legal behavior, which consists in the implementation of universal legal education, overcoming legal nihilism, the formation of law-abiding behavior.</p>
<p>Mehnat ta'limi - o'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning umumiy mehnat ko'nikmalari va ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan birgalikdagi faoliyati, psixol ishga tayyorlik, ishga va uning mahsulotiga, kasbni ongli ravishda tanlashga mas'uliyatli munosabatni shakllantirish.</p>	<p>Labor education is a joint activity of teachers and students aimed at developing general work skills and abilities, psychological readiness for work, the formation of a responsible attitude to work and its products, the conscious choice of profession.</p>
<p>Aqliy ta'lim - shaxsning intellektual madaniyati, kognitiv motivlari, aqliy kuchlari, tafakkuri, dunyoqarashi va intellektual erkinligining shakllanishi.</p>	<p>Mental education is the formation of an individual's intellectual culture, cognitive motives, mental powers, thinking, worldview and intellectual freedom.</p>
<p>Jismoniy ta'lim-tarbiya - jismoniy rivojlanish, salomatlikni mustahkamlash, yuqori ko'rsatkichlarni ta'minlash va doimiy jismoniy o'zini takomillashtirishga ehtiyojni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan shaxsni takomillashtirish tizimi.</p>	<p>Physical education is a system of personal development aimed at developing physical development, strengthening health, ensuring high performance and the need for continuous physical self-improvement.</p>

<p>Badiiy ta'lim - o'quvchilarda san'atni his qilish, tushunish, baholash, sevish, undan zavq olish, badiiy va ijodiy faoliyatga, estetik qadriyatlarni yaratish ehtiyojlarini rivojlantirish.</p>	<p>Art education is the development of students' need to feel, understand, appreciate, love art, enjoy it, engage in artistic and creative activities, and create aesthetic values.</p>
<p>Ekologik ta'lim - yosh avlod o'rtasida tabiat haqidagi bilimlarni va unga insonparvarlik, mas'uliyatli munosabatni yuqori milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyat sifatida o'z ichiga olgan yuqori ekologik madaniyatni maqsadli rivojlantirish.</p>	<p>Ecological education is the purposeful development of a high ecological culture among the younger generation, which includes knowledge of nature and a humane, responsible attitude to it as a high national and universal value.</p>
<p>Iqtisodiy ta'lim - ishlab chiqarishni, tarqatish va iste'molni oqilona boshqarish va tashkil etishning tabiati, tamoyillari va me'yorlariga mos keladigan bilim, ko'nikma va ko'nikmalarni, ehtiyojlarni, qiziqish va fikrlash uslubini shakllantirishga qaratilgan o'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning maqsadli o'zaro ta'siri.</p>	<p>Economic education is the teaching and learning process aimed at forming knowledge, skills and abilities, needs, interests and ways of thinking that meet the nature, principles and norms of rational management and organization of production, distribution and consumption. Targeted interaction of students.</p>
<p>Estetik tarbiya - tarbiyachilar va o'quvchilarning maqsadli o'zaro ta'siri, o'sib borayotgan odamda hayotda va san'atda go'zallikni idrok etish, to'g'ri tushunish, qadrlash va yaratish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish va takomillashtirishga, ijodkorlikda, go'zallik qonunlariga muvofiq ijod qilishda yordam beradi.</p>	<p>Aesthetic education is a purposeful interaction of educators and students to develop and improve the ability of a growing person to perceive, understand, appreciate and create beauty in life and art, in creativity, go Helps to create according to the laws of nature.</p>

Pedagogical terminology implements its integration features and functional features in a multicultural information, research and educational space. It affects the elements of its system, the contradictions that occur between them, and the changes that occur as a result of these contradictions. These changes affect both its formal quantitative and qualitative content characteristics.

Modern ideas about the essence, tasks and integrative characteristics of pedagogical terminology allow to define it as an integral open system.

Pedagogical terminology as a system includes and serves individual terms and terminological systems that are conditionally related to the concept and subject of pedagogical activity. To identify, systematize, store and transmit scientific and pedagogical information in a single multicultural research and education space. The

current level of development of information and communication technologies is changing the idea of the possibility of determining the spatial and temporal dynamics of international pedagogy. Terminology, its systematization, coordination, storage and transfer to a single multicultural field of global computer communications. This allows the creation of different types of pedagogical lexicography, reveals physical resources in the global system, including electronic interdisciplinary and intercultural connections.

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